

Exploring Types and Characteristics of Product Forms in Eliciting a User's Pleasure

Wen-chieh Chang, Graduate School of Design, National Taiwan University of Science and Technology – Taiwan

Tyan Yu Wu, The department of Industrial Design, Chang Gung University – Taiwan

Abstract

Incorporating emotional value into products has become an essential weapon in increasing a product's competitive edge in the consumer market. Consumers are especially drawn to products that look 'pleasurable'. It is therefore important for product designers to understand 'how' a user's emotion affects his/her appraisal of a product at the point of purchase, so that they can embed characteristics that evoke 'pleasure' into the product during the design process. Consequently, the aim of this study is to investigate the types and characteristics of product forms which can elicit a user's pleasurable emotion during their visual appraisal process.

An in-depth interview was conducted in order to collect the responses of pleasurable feelings from 22 participants. 19 stimuli were selected from 262 images and used for the interviews. Keywords from their answers were detected and used for content analysis. After examination, 15 characteristics that described the 'pleasures' of product form were found and categorized into 6 types of pleasurable form: Bios form, Cultural form, Aesthetic form, Decorative form, Unique form and Ideal form. The explanation of 6 types of pleasurable form and their characteristics and the discussion can provide designers a basic framework to develop pleasurable products.

Keywords: Pleasure, emotion, product form

Introduction

Desmet (2001) showed that products could elicit strong emotional responses. The results of Jordan's research (1998) in human factors also illustrated that the first three product properties that significantly affected users' emotion were 'features', 'usability' and 'aesthetics'. Both features and aesthetics apparently have a strong connection with a product's appearance. He suggested that a product with pleasantness was used more regularly, and that future purchasing decisions would be affected by the level of pleasure a product provided to its user (Jordan, 1998). In addition, the research from Creusen and Snelders demonstrated that people who scored high on the hedonic scale were indeed more interested in the attributes that described the product's form (Cresuen, 2002).

To understand how the product elicit positive emotion, Janlert (1997) described that things appear to have character- high-level attributes that help us understand and relate to them. Furthermore, he stated that the attribution of character to an artifact could be based on

different aspects of the artifact. A car for instance, with rounded forms and warm colours suggests that it has a warm, friendly and protective character. A designer may try to exploit dependencies between appearances and perceived character. By manipulating the appearance, a designer hopes to evoke certain emotions or induce certain beliefs in the user (Janlert, 1997).

These research findings imply the importance of product form with respect to the pleasure of products. However, the lacking of the understanding of pleasurable products and their forms may have a restriction in design process. This study tends to bridge the gap by exploring the types and characteristics, clearing their relationship and providing designers a reference during design practicing.

The definition of pleasurable product form

The Oxford English Dictionary defines pleasure as ‘ the condition of consciousness or sensation by the enjoyment or anticipation of what is felt or viewed as good or desirable; enjoyment, delight, gratification’. Jordan (1999) states that pleasure-based approaches to product design can be seen as approaches that consider the full potential benefits that a product can deliver. Combined with previous definition, in this study, pleasurable product form is defined as ‘the form of products that can elicit pleasure through the visual perception of product appearance and their meaning.’

Appraisal theory

Appraisal theory contains three dimensions: concern, stimulus and appraisal. Every emotion conceals a concern which is either a more or less stable preference for certain states of the world (Frijda, 1986, Desmet, 2002). Stimuli that match our concerns are appraised as beneficial. At this point, a consumer might elicit an emotion (e.g. pleasure, joyful, happy) if it is appraised as relevant to the consumer’s concern (Desmet, 2002).

Based on the emotional appraisal model created by Desmet & Hekkert, the model applied to this study focuses on only one positive emotion, which is elicited through an appraisal process. Therefore, a consumer’s pleasure can be elicited, if his or her concerns to the product form (stimulus) are a visual match through the appraisal process (See Dia. 1). The items of

‘concern’ and ‘appraisal’ are summarized from the theories of Desmet (2003), Scherer (2001), Frijda (1986), Smith & Ellsworth (1987) and Roseman (2001). The concerns involve goal, standard, attitude, novelty and needs. Goal can refer to state of affairs that we want to obtain, i.e. how we would like things to be. Standard can refer to how we believe things should be. Attitude can refer to users’ dispositional likings for certain objects or attributes of an object. This can be with respect to aspects or features of products such as product colour or material senses. Novelty can refer to any product (feature) that is appraised as novel; and needs can refer to the need of stimulation (Desmet, 2003).

Figure 1, Cognitive Appraisal Model for Pleasure

Method

Twenty-two interviewees with an average age of 32 years (12 senior designers, 10 design-related individuals) responded to an in-depth interview. 12 out of 22 interviewees have practiced design for at least 8 years and 9 of them work as design manager in large firms. 262 stimulus images were collected from three major international competitions and large companies, comprising ‘iF’ (2002) 27 pieces, ‘IDEA’ (2002) 56 pieces, ‘G-Mark’ (2002) 63 pieces and IBM, PHILIPS, ALESSI, APPLE 116 pieces.

Upon commencement the definition of a ‘pleasurable product’ was explained to the interviewees. By perceiving the product images, they were then asked to group the 262 pieces into three categories: ‘pleasure’, ‘displeasure’ and ‘neutral’ and, then to rank them intuitively from the ‘pleasurable’ group only. Nineteen pieces were selected for a further in-depth interview. The interviewees were asked to watch these 19 stimuli and elaborate “why they derived pleasure from the stimulus after visually perceiving the images?” The interviewees’ responses were recorded for content analysis.

The application of appraisal theory

The appraisal theory is the base of analysis process. The keywords from the interviewees' responses were sorted by reference to their concern (e.g. goal, standard, attitude and needs) and appraisal (e.g. motive compliance, legitimacy, intrinsic pleasantness, novelty and challenge), which were extracted from emotion appraisal theory. For example, concerning a product, an interviewee might make an appraisal if products are pleasant or not in relation to personal concern (attitude). In this case, responses relating to the attitude keyword addressed by interviewees related to meanings such as 'like', 'nice', 'beautiful' and 'personality'; and when an interviewee described that s/he felt pleasure because of the 'beauty of product shape', the response was grouped within the category concerning attitude related contents. The outcomes showed that descriptions regarding color, material and shape traits can be grouped into one category and the name, 'Aesthetic form', was given to this category at the end. Following this process, all responses were analyzed and identified based on the 5 concerns and appraisal keywords in table 1. The analysis, identification and grouping of keywords were completed with the assistance of a senior design professional. The results evidenced that 15 characteristics were found and 6 types of pleasurable form were then classified from these characteristics. 6 types of pleasurable form were Bios, Culture, Aesthetic, Decoration, Unique and Ideal form (See Table 1).

Concerns	Appraise	Keywords of appraise	Characteristics	Types of Pleasurable form
Needs	Challenge	Fascination, inspiration, looks-like	Bios-shape Bios-action Bios-image	Bios form
Standard	Legitimacy	Should, ought to, justified	Symbolic meaning Style recognition Literary meaning	Cultural form
Attitude	Intrinsic pleasantness	Like, nice, beautiful, love, personality	Color trait Material trait Shape trait	Aesthetic form
Attitude	Intrinsic pleasantness	Beautiful, display	Display effect Playful effect	Decorative form
	Novelty	Strange, unexpected, odd, sudden	Unique idea Unique material Unique shape	Unique form
Goal	Motive compliance	Want, need, like to, yearn, desirability, expecting	Preference achievement	Ideal form

Table 1, the keywords of appraisal theory and the type of pleasurable form

Six types of pleasurable form

Bios form

Consumers have a tendency and need to experience stimulus (i.e. product form) and this involves imagination, fascination and inspiration towards the feature/s of product forms. Imagination may result in a pleasurable response. The response of the interviewees demonstrated that bios-form could elicit humor and an interesting effect whilst product shape, action and image were associated with relevant contents/images in consumers' mind. In this study, the contents involved animals, plants and human figures. The fascinating bios-forms thus inspired consumers with a pleasing experience. Three characteristics were concluded from the responses, and they were 'bios-shapes', 'bios-actions' and 'bios-images'.

'Bios-shape' mimics or applies to a product's form, the shape of biological features or formations. The responses showed that the shape of humans, animals and plants often applied to products can be identified, for example, the Sugar Bowl produced by Alessi (Pic. 1) which has an 'upside-down-cone' body with three frog-like legs. Interviewees were fascinated with the funny legs as they elicited pleasure.

'Bios-action' mimics or implicates product form through the action of biological features or formations. The results showed that the action of humans and animals applied to products can be identified. Magic Bunny, a toothpick bottle for example (Pic. 2), emphasizes 'rabbit ears' as a metaphor of its catch and pull-up use procedure. This operation process creates a funny interaction which also elicits pleasure.

'Bios-image' is concerned with the image transformation from humans, animals and plants into a product shape, such as 'Globo' teapot's form that creates an inspirational image similar to a puppy-like shape, reinforced by associations with the legs, tail and mouth of a puppy (Pic. 3). This visual interaction with consumers elicited pleasure in the manner of inspiration.

Cultural form

Standard is the belief, norm, or traditional identification of consumers to products. Educator, Aspin, claims that culture is the co-influence among social rules, language and art forms. A personal interpretation regarding the meaning of life and value is then constructed from those influences (Best, 1992). Cultural form is one with 'social meaning' and which can best fit social belief systems, values and custom contexts. Consumers base judgments on the

understanding of cultural experience and value, and appraise the meaning of form and function of products in terms of legitimacy. The keywords of appraisal can be associated with 'ought to' and 'justified'. Consumers are concerned with the 'meaning' of form, to confirm if it matches with cultural standards, and only when the two match do they feel pleasure. The results showed that 3 characteristics could be identified – 'symbolised meaning', 'style recognition' and 'literary meaning'.

'Style recognition' deals with style identification and personal recognition. Style is fashion which has lasted for a prolonged lifecycle (Lin, 2002). Each person identifies with his/her favourite style in daily life. The recognition is the product, which has commonness and legitimacy (Hsiau-lin, 1991). For example, many consumers have a preference for unique materials, like those used in the Apple I-Mac (Pic. 4), and believe that particular materials represent contemporary style, which in turn elicits pleasantness, and a certain product style can represent personal taste and tendencies towards current trends.

'Symbolic meaning' is a way to represent a special meaning through an object. It can even illustrate a more powerful meaning than the object itself in an artistic creation. A consumer might feel additional pleasure towards a product if they can interpret and recognise its symbolic meaning. Jim Nature TV (Pic. 5), designed by Starck is constructed from compressed woodchips and plastic, this product not only shows the material's natural beauty and form, but also demonstrates a symbolic meaning in using ecologically-friendly materials. Consumers warm to this design because they believe that they should be concerned with environmental issues and this concern in particular makes them feel pleasant and virtuous when they use it.

'Literary meaning' deals with the use of language or other methods as a sign to deliver cultural value to consumers. The feature of product form should be a sign which can convey meaning or tell a story to the user. This information elicits pleasure when the content is interpreted correctly. For instance, consumers feel a sense of fun when using 'Magic Bunny', toothpick container. The rabbit form and tube shape implies its operating process and serves as a story-telling metaphor to prompt the user's imagination whilst using the product.

Aesthetic form

Attitude encapsulates intrinsic pleasantness. Interviewees had certain attitudes with respect to

aspects or features of products such as material and colour. Product or aspects of products can be appraised as such in terms of their 'appealingness'. Appraisal's keywords can be associated with 'like', or 'love' the appearance of a product's form. Three characteristics of aesthetics were found – 'colour', 'material' and 'shape' traits.

'Colour trait' can elicit pleasure by visually stimulating consumers by the product's colour. Product colour can deliver the first impression to the viewers to elicit emotion at a sensational level. Consumers have strong impressions regarding colour perception. Interviewees favoured colours in many ways such as 'an abundance of colours', 'natural colour' and 'tempting' colours to elicit pleasure. The glamorous colours of iMac for example deliver warm and sweet images which in turn generate pleasure.

'Material trait' can elicit pleasure through visual interaction with material. Interviewees described that transparent materials provided a strong visual impact. Hence, they preferred semi-transparent materials because of their lightweight, high-tech-look and uniqueness. This evidenced that a good combination of different materials in a product can elicit pleasure because of their expressive qualities and beauty of mixed materials. Interviewees described that Starck's Jim Nature TV constructed from woodchips and plastic panels provided beauty by means of the quality of the mixed materials. Pleasure caused by unique materials has a great impact on viewer's sensations.

'Shape trait' of a product can elicit pleasure through stimulating form. Interviewees described that a soft, elegant, well proportioned shape provided a good visual experience and elicited pleasure. For instance, the radio (Pic. 6) composed of two round shapes and simple curves, provided a beautiful and simple shape that elicited pleasure through its aesthetic appeal.

Decorative form

Consumers prefer to choose and develop their own life style and collect artifacts that become an extension of their personal style. People display products to represent their style. Research shows that a product plays an important role in a consumers' living environment. Lowry (1976) stated that both artists and designers have the same process and intention to deliver their visual concept to the viewer. Interviewees had a tendency to project the products into their own environment and did consider objects as 'things' they could share with visitors. Hence, a good product, like a painting, should allow consumers to display it as a part of home

decoration to illustrate owner's taste and personal style. Furthermore, the displayed object becomes a medium to increase 'pleasure' and 'life quality' in a social interaction aspect. This type of product is classified into two characteristics – 'display effect' and 'playful effect'.

'Display effect' is a product's characteristic which can be classified as part of the decoration in our living environment. Interviewees commented that the form between 'abstract' and 'concrete', such as sculpture, allow viewers a variety of imaginative ways to appreciate a product. This visual interactive process provides an opportunity to give the user 'pleasantness'. The Juicer (Pic. 7) for example, designed by Starck has a fantasy form with refined proportions and an elegant shape. Besides its function, the Juicer can serve the dual purpose of an artistic sculpture to display in the home. For the consumer, pleasure is provided by allowing individuals to enjoy making juice and appreciate the work of art simultaneously.

'Playful effect', like a toy, is the characteristic of a product as an interesting object in the house. It joins other displayed objects to fulfill pleasant visual sensations, and is also an interactive object to satiate interactive desires. Hence, consumers can experience pleasure both by interaction with the products physically and visually. For instance, Magic Bunny, a toothpick bottle, can be a medium to spur the imagination and playfulness on the dining table through interaction.

Unique form

Novelty is a characteristic that deals with a product which has a creative and unique emphasis on concept, form, issues and methods of feedback. Consumers have tendencies to be curious or attracted to products with novelty value and have positive affection towards creative products. This type of product is classified by three properties – 'unique idea', 'unique material' and 'unique form'.

'Unique form' is concerned with new shape creation. Consumers expect to have a surprise when perceiving something different or new. The Nike watches (Pic. 8) utilize a diagonal shape on their display to provide a comfortable reading angle. This dynamic and creative form is considered to be a functional and aesthetically beautiful product and yet, can elicit pleasure.

'Unique materials' deal with new developments in material science, manufacturing

technology and the images of materials. Compared with traditional plastic materials, consumers consider transparent materials to be unique and creative in current product designs, and prefer products using these materials because of their soft and modern look. The innovation of using unique materials also provides a new image which elicits surprise and pleasure.

‘Unique idea’ is concerned with a product’s new solution of operation or function. Consumers prefer new and smart solutions to old problems. For instance, the toilet brush design provides a new way to handle the product and accommodate usage without smearing the user’s hands. This creative idea elicits pleasure through both beautiful form and smart function.

Ideal form

Goal is the final result of individual activity through motivation (Chang, 1989). The key words of appraisal regarding goal are indicated as needs, desire, want and like. It impacts the affection of consumers when product form matches the goal of the consumer’s expectation. This study shows that one characteristic is concluded - ‘preference achievement’.

‘Preference achievement’ is a personal preference with regards to a product’s form. The preferable form can result in pleasure when the goal is achieved. A consumer, for instance might experience pleasure when his or her expectations of having a stylish computer mouse are fulfilled by receiving a unique one constructed out of a transparent material (Pic. 9), one which complies with his/her ideal/preferable style.

Picture 1,
Sugar Bowl

Picture 2,
Toothpick bottle

Picture 3,
Globo teapot

Picture 4,
Apple I-Mac

Picture 5,
Jim Nature TV

Picture 6,
Radio

Picture 7,
Juicer

Picture 8,
Nike watches

Picture 9,
Mouse

Figure 2

Discussion

This study's results illustrated types, characteristics and their relationships towards pleasurable forms, and these outcomes should provide a guideline for designers to create a 'product with pleasure'.

Firstly, this paper finds with respect to responses that keywords related to Aesthetic and Bios form were the most frequently used, and this is evidenced by the 46 keywords used to describe Bios form and the 43 keywords describing Aesthetic form, whilst Decorative, Unique, Cultural and Ideal form were described by the lower 29, 28, 21, 5 keywords respectively. This evidence clearly implies that Aesthetic and Bios form emphasize the message of explicit form traits (e.g. material, shape and colour) which have higher tendencies to grab consumers' visual attention and elicit pleasure.

Secondly, concerning 'visual perception' toward a product's form, evidence shows that there are two levels in the perceiving process towards pleasurable form. The results demonstrated that different product form characteristics deliver different levels of information, which in turn elicits different levels of pleasure to consumers. The Magic bunny for example, has different levels of pleasure - on one hand, consumers feel pleasure, which is caused by explicit information such as material, colour and bios-shape, and on the other, pleasure is also

created by implicit information such as the metaphoric story. Extending the first discussion, this result implies that pleasure elicited by explicit information (e.g. Bios and Aesthetic form) is easier to catch interviewees' visual attention than pleasure elicited by implicit information (e.g. Cultural form).

Thirdly, the results demonstrated that some products had multiple pleasurable forms, showing that in 20 cases, a product appeared to have both 'Aesthetic' form and 'Bios' form and in 15 appeared to have both 'Aesthetic' and 'Unique' form. For instance, interviewees described that Starck's Juicer demonstrated different types of pleasurable form such as Aesthetic, Bios and Unique form. This result implies that a consumer can perceive multiple pleasures towards the same product and elicit pleasure.

Fourthly, it is noteworthy that cognition appraisal theory provides a useful model in identifying the types and characteristics of pleasurable form, which can elicit a consumer's pleasure. The conclusion of 6 pleasurable forms and 15 characteristics, by manipulating them should be able to provide designers with a variety of directions to create ideas with pleasurable characteristics. However, the complex relationship between individual users and product forms involves a sophisticated perception process and it is necessary to conduct further in-depth research and experiments to clearly identify each type of pleasurable form and their relationships.

Lastly, it is also notable that the discussed types of pleasurable form do not claim to cover all possibilities of pleasurable form since interviewee catchments were not broad enough to represent the wider ranging population as evidently individuals have unique characteristics, perceptions and cultural backgrounds. How to identify and generalize a product with visual pleasant commonality in a big market needs is a challenge and ripe for future research.

REFERENCES

- Abrecht, Donald, Lupton, Ellen, and Holt, S. Steven. 2000. *Design Culture Now*. London: Laurence King.
- Best, David. 1992. *The Rationality of Feeling*. Taipei: Psychological Publishing Co.
- Chang, T.S. 1989. *Chang's Psychology Dictionary*. Taipei: Tun-Hau publisher.
- Coates, Del. 2002. *Watches tell more than time*. NY: McGraw-Hill.
- Creusen, Marielle, and Snelders, Dirk. 2002. *Product Appearance and Consumer Pleasure*. UK : Taylor and Francis.
- Crozier, Ray. 1994. *Manufactured pleasures*. NY: Manchester University Press.
- Dalgleish, Tim. 1999. *Handbook of Cognition and Emotion*. New York: John Wiley & Sons.
- Desmet, Pieter. 2002. *Designing Emotions*. Delft, NL.
- Desmet, Pieter. 2003. *A Multilayered Model of Product Emotions*. UK: The Design Journal.
- Desmet, Pieter, and Overbeeke, Kees. 2001. *Designing Products with Added Emotional Value: Research through Design*. The Design Journal, 4 (1): 32-47.
- Ekman, Paul. 1994. *The Nature of Emotion*. NY: Oxford Univ.
- Gobe, Marc. 2001. *Emotional branding*. NY: Leviathan.
- Gosling, C.B.J. 1969. *Pleasure and Desire*. Oxford: Clarendonpress.
- Green, S. William, and Jordan, W. Patrick edited. 2002. *Pleasure with products Beyond Usabilit*. London: Taylor and Francis.
- Hsau Lin Chung Shun. 1991. *The psychology of form constructure*. Taipei: E Fong Tan Publisher.
- Khalid, M. Halimahtun. 2001. *Can Customer Needs Express Affective Design*. International Conference on Affective Human Factors Design, Singapore: Asean Academic Press.
- Janlert, Lers-Erick. 1997. *The Character of Things*. Design Studies, 18 (3): 297-314.
- Jordan, Patrick. 1998. *Human Factors for Pleasure in Product use, Applied Ergonomics*, 29 (1): 25-33.
- Jordan, Patrick. 2000. *Designing Pleasurable Products*. UK: Taylor and Francis.
- Kau, H.Y. 2002. *Sociology of Fashion*. Taipei: Yang-Chih Publisher.
- Lazarus S. Richard 1991. *Emotion & Adaptation*, New York: Oxford University Press, Inc.

Lazarus, S. Richard, and Lazarus, N.B. 1994. *Passion and Reason*. NY: Oxford University Press.

Lin, Chien-Huang. 2002. *Consumer Behavior*. Taipei: Bestwise Publisher.

Lowry, Bates, and Du, Z.G. Translated. 1976. *The Visual Experience*. Taipei: Lion Publishing.

Marberry, O. Sara, and Zagon, Laurie. 1995. *The Power of Color*. New York: John Wiley Sons, Inc.

Norman, A. Donald. 2004. *Emotional Design*. New Yor: Basic Books.

Sweet, Fay. 1999. *Frog: Form follows Emotion*. London: Thames and Hudson.

Stongman, K. T. 1996. *the Psychology of Emotion*. NY: John Wiley & Sons.

Tiger, Lionel 2000. *the Pursuit of Pleasure*. London: Transaction.

Velde, P.B. and Fiddler, S.G. 2002. *Lifestyle Performance*. USA: SLACK.

Dr. Wen-chih Chang earned his Master Degree in Industrial Design at Syracuse University, N.Y., USA in 1980. Since then, he has been an industrial design teacher and product designer. In 1993 he gained his doctorate in Design management at the Manchester Metropolitan University, UK. Being a design consultant for many companies and for many years gives him opportunity to have a closer look at the design practice in business world. He specializes in the research of product design management (e.g. design strategy, design quality, organizational creativity and product design performance) and the relationship between product image and product form feature.

Wu, Tyan Yu currently teaches Industrial Design in Chang Gung University since 1997. Before his teaching career, he had been worked with Kemnitzer Design, Blue Leaf design, Tatung Telecom in United States as an Industrial Designer. He graduated from University of Bridgeport with BS degree and earned a MA degree from San Jose State University in USA, 1994. He received IDSA Student Chapter, Merit Award in 1991 and was IDSA, ASME, member in 1992, 1998, and CIDA, CID member since 2000. Currently, he is studying his Ph.D. in National Taiwan University of Science and Technology. His interested research areas are pleasurable product and Taiwanese aboriginal culture in design.